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How renewable is the global electricity system? An assessment of the evolution of renewability between 1900-2050

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1. Introduction

The global electricity system depends on fossil fuels and other non-renewable energies, not only for the direct use of fuels, but also for the manufacture of the materials required to build the energy infrastructure. The importance of infrastructure will increase due to the large amount of materials needed in renewable energy technologies capable of capturing the free renewable energy available in nature. Based on this context and on the IEA's Net-Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario, this study applies the novel renewable exergy return on investment (RExROI) metric to assess the evolution of the global electricity system for the 1900-2050's period. RExROI measures the amount of renewable exergy returned by investing one unit of non-renewable exergy, both as fuel and embodied in the infrastructure materials. The results indicate that from 2027 onwards the RExROI begins to be greater than zero, i.e. the global electricity system becomes renewable. RExROI from this year onwards grows strongly due to the energy transition to reach 7.18 MJ/MJ in 2050, i.e. 7.18 MJ of renewable exergy is captured for each non-renewable MJ invested. However, considering only non-renewable infrastructure due to renewable technologies, the RExROI would increase to 31.75 MJ/MJ. The RExROI concept can be considered as a Renewation Index (RI), applicable to any energy system and even to society as a whole. Thus, societies with a negative RExROI or close to zero are not guaranteed to endure in the long term because they destroy non-renewable resources that will eventually become depleted. Increasing RExROI is therefore of vital importance for the sustainability of any society.

Keywords: Exergy, Exergy Cost, Electricity, Infrastructure, RExROI.

2. Methodology

The methodology of this study is based on two previous papers: "Non-renewable and renewable levelized exergy cost of electricity (LExCOE) with focus on its infrastructure: 1900–2050" [1] and "Renewable exergy return on investment (RExROI) in energy systems. The case of silicon photovoltaic panels" [2]. The first study calculated the exergy cost of electricity disaggregated in non-renewable and renewable sources, and the second paper established the calculation of the renewable exergy return on investment (RExROI).

Non-Renewable and Renewable Exergy Cost of Electricity

Figure 1 shows the disaggregated exergy cost of electricity between 1900 and 2050. This graph is directly extracted from the study [1]. The solid Black line indicates the electricity produced each year, which we denote as EL_i , where i refers to a given year. On the other hand, the bars indicate the exergy cost of electricity in a given year i , which we denote as B_i^* . The exergy cost represents the cumulative consumption of exergy to produce a commodity. [3]. In this study the commodity is electricity.

Figure 1 shows the exergy cost classified into six categories ("REN Fuel", "REN Infrás.", "NUC Fuel", "NUC Infrás.", "FF fuel", "FF Infrás."). Thus, 'REN' refers to all exergy cost with a renewable origin, 'NUC' to exergy cost with a nuclear origin and 'FF' to exergy cost with a fossil fuel origin. Therefore, the categories 'NUC' and 'FF' are non-renewable. In addition to the origin of the exergy cost, it is also differentiated whether the exergy cost is used as fuels ('Fuel') or as infrastructure ('Infrás.'). Thus, 'Fuel' implies a direct use, i.e. the fuel, whether fossil, nuclear or renewable (e.g. sunlight or kinetic energy of the wind), is used during that year to produce the electricity. On the other hand, 'Infrás.' implies an indirect use, i.e. the fuels are used for the production of materials that constitute the infrastructure to produce the electricity.

The study [1] considered 34 materials: Ag, Al, Au, B, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Dy, Fe, In, Li, Mg, Mn, Mo, Nb, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Si, Sn, Ta, Tb, Ti, Zn, steel (unalloyed, low alloy and stainless), concrete, plastic, glass and solar glass. Thus, the exergy to manufacture these materials of the infrastructure was considered. In this respect it is important to note that a considerable part of the exergy to manufacture the materials is electricity. Therefore, a feedback loop is observed: the exergy cost of electricity (separated into non-renewable and renewable) in a given year is used to produce the materials in the following year, which affects the exergy cost of electricity in that year, and so on. Thus, the category 'REN Infrás.' is produced by the renewable part of the electricity that is used in the manufacture of the materials. Because of this feedback loop it is important to use as historical data as possible. Therefore, the study [1] used historical data between 1900 and 2017 from [4], and then used the Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario from the International Energy Agency (IEA) [5]. This scenario represents a strong deployment of renewable technologies, as illustrated in Figure 1 with the increase in the contribution of the 'REN' category to the exergy cost.

Figure 1. Exergy cost of electricity between 1900-2050.

The RExROI calculation is based solely on the exergy from non-renewable sources and the amount of electricity which can be generated. Therefore, this study uses electricity production in a given year i (EL_i) and the non-renewable exergy cost ($B_{NR_i}^*$) employed in one year. The term $B_{NR_i}^*$ represents the sum of the exergy cost of the categories 'NUC Fuel', 'NUC Infrás.', 'FF Fuel', and 'FF Infrás.'.

Renewable Exergy Return on Investment (RExROI)

RExROI represents the amount of net renewable exergy that can be captured by an energy system for each unit of non-renewable exergy invested in it, either in the form of fuel or infrastructure [2]. It is calculated with equation 1, using the parameters EL_i y $B_{NR_i}^*$ from Figure 1.

$$RExROI_i = \frac{EL_i - B_{NR_i}^*}{B_{NR_i}^*} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

A negative RExROI indicates that the energy system is non-renewable and that for each unit of exergy it generates, it destroys a certain amount of non-renewable exergy. Conversely, a positive RExROI indicates that the energy system captures renewable exergy.

3. Results

Figure 2 shows the results of equation 1 using the data in Figure 1. Figure 2 is divided into two sections for analysis: the first between 1900 and 2010 which is shown expanded in Figure 2 itself, the second between 2010 and 2050 which is shown expanded in Figure 3.

The period between 1900 and 2010 is characterized by relatively constant RExROI values ranging from -0.7 MJ/MJ to -0.5 MJ/MJ. In this period RExROI is always negative, i.e. for every MJ of electricity produced, between 0.70 and 0.53 MJ of non-renewable exergy is destroyed. This is significant because non-renewable exergy cannot be replenished in the short term and is therefore no longer available for future generations. Thus, these resources can be considered to be lost forever. This is because in the period 1900-2010 most generation was of fossil origin and the deployment of renewables was practically reduced to hydroelectricity.

Figure 2. Renewable exergy return on investment (RExROI) of global electricity between 1900-2050 under Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario from the International Energy Agency (IEA).

Figure 3. Renewable exergy return on investment (RExROI) of global electricity between 2010-2050 under Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario from the International Energy Agency (IEA).

The period between 2010 and 2050 is shown in Figure 3. For analysis purposes, it has been subdivided into three periods: 2010-2027, 2027-2041 and 2041-2050, as shown in Figure 3.

The sub-period between 2010 and 2027 is characterized by the beginning of the energy transition. At this point it is important to mention that the data are historical up to 2017, and that from this year onwards the NZE scenario of the IEA starts. Thus, between 2010 and 2020 the RExROI changes from -0.53 MJ/MJ to -0.44 MJ/MJ, i.e. it increases at a linear rate of 0.0089 MJ/MJ per year. Although the change may seem small, a trend change from the rest of the history (years 1900-2010 in Figure 2) is beginning to be observed. This is due to the fact that from 2010 onwards new renewable technologies, especially wind and photovoltaic, started to be deployed. However, a more significant change is seen between 2020 and 2027. During this period, RExROI increases the rate of increase to 0.0572 MJ/MJ per year, from -0.44 MJ/MJ to -0.04 MJ/MJ, although the improvement is almost linear. The year 2027 is important, as it is the last year with a negative RExROI.

The sub-period between 2027 and 2041 shows a change in trend compared to the previous ones. At this stage, RExROI increases exponentially at a rate of 33% per year. Thus, it goes from just 0.04 MJ/MJ in 2027 to 6.11 MJ/MJ in 2041. This sharp change in trend is due to the strong deployment of renewables, especially wind and photovoltaic technologies, according to the IEA NZE scenario used in this study. In parallel to this deployment of renewables, fossil technologies such as coal and natural gas are also starting to be decommissioned, further boosting RExROI growth.

The sub-period between 2041-2050 shows a stabilization in RExROI growth, returning to linear growth, from 6.11 MJ/MJ in 2041 to 7.18 MJ/MJ in 2050, i.e. increasing at a rate of 0.11 MJ/MJ per year. This slowdown in growth is because, in the previous phase

(2027-2041), non-renewable technologies were largely abandoned and the deployment of renewable infrastructures was already underway.

In 2050, 91% of electricity already originates from renewable sources, according to the IEA's NZE scenario. Thus, most of the infrastructure exergy cost is accounted for by these technologies, as the infrastructure exergy cost of non-renewable technologies is very low compared to renewable technologies and, moreover, non-renewable technologies only contribute to 9% of electricity. The infrastructure exergy cost in 2050 amounts to $9.69E+12$ MJ of which $7.23E+12$ MJ are non-renewable, i.e. 75%, and $2.37E+14$ MJ of electricity is produced in this year. Therefore, if we calculate the RExROI in 2050 using only the non-renewable infrastructure, which belongs almost entirely to renewable technologies, we obtain a value of 31.75 MJ/MJ. While the value of 7.18 MJ/MJ is the overall RExROI, the value of 31.75 MJ/MJ refers to the RExROI of renewable technologies, as it only considers infrastructure. Thus, renewable technologies can capture about 32 MJ of renewable exergy for every MJ of non-renewable exergy that is invested in infrastructure. In other words, to produce 1 MJ of renewable exergy requires 0.03 MJ of non-renewable exergy that is used to produce the materials for the infrastructure. Therefore, the dependence of renewable technologies on fossil fuels continues, although in a reduced form.

4. Conclusions

Electricity production traditionally has required non-renewable exergy. However, the energy transition aims to reduce the amount of non-renewable exergy used through the deployment of renewable technologies capable of capturing renewable exergy from nature, such as sunlight or the kinetic energy of wind. However, these technologies also need non-renewable exergy throughout their life cycle. This study considers the non-renewable exergy used to produce the metals and materials that constitute the electrical infrastructure, as well as the non-renewable exergy used as fuel in conventional power plants. To show the renewability of the electricity system as a whole, the RExROI is used. This indicator shows the amount of net renewable exergy captured by an energy system for each unit of non-renewable exergy invested in it. Applying this indicator to the global electricity system between 1900 and 2010, it is observed that it maintains negative between -0.7 to -0.5 MJ/MJ. However, from 2010 onwards, it starts to increase until -0.44 MJ/MJ in 2020. Between 2020 and 2027, the increase gains momentum with an annual increase of 0.0572 MJ/MJ, becoming positive in 2028. In other words, from this year onwards, the global electricity system starts to become renewable under the IEA NZE scenario used in this study. Between 2027 and 2041, the RExROI growth rate becomes exponential with a 33% increase from 0.04 MJ/MJ to 6.11 MJ/MJ. In the last stage studied (2041-2050), RExROI growth slows down because it is during the previous stage (2027-2041) that most of the decommissioning of non-renewable technologies occurs, reaching 7.18 MJ/MJ in 2050. Thus, by 2050, 91% of electricity comes from renewable technologies. However, the non-renewable exergy cost of infrastructure remains. As a result, for every MJ of renewable exergy, 0.03 MJ of non-renewable exergy is required for infrastructure, leaving a RExROI of about 32 MJ/MJ for renewable technologies.

Finally, RExROI can be considered a Renewability Index (RI) that is applicable to any energy production system, indicating the degree of renewability of these technologies. Its message is powerful because it can be extrapolated to any energy system and even to society as a whole. Societies have always needed energy, so this index can indicate how far our society is from a fully renewable society. Thus, a value close to zero or negative indicates a society that destroys the planet's non-renewable resources and will eventually be depleted. But a society with high RExROI values could sustain itself in the long run. It must be said that Nature has an infinite RI; it is completely renewable, even when supplied with its inorganic nutrients, biomass, or water, sunlight allows it to close the cycles without burning any non-renewable energy.

5. References

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